

References

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Gravimetric Determination of Rhodium with Ligand 1-Imino-3-Thioisindoline

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THE ligand 1-imino-3-thioisindoline has recently been used for the gravimetric determination of Cu(II) by Nigam and Tiwari¹. In the present investigation the same ligand has been further used for the gravimetric determination of rhodium. Investigations have indicated that the ligand reacts with Rh³⁺ ions at pH ranging from 7.5 to 10.0 giving precipitate of insoluble metal complex.

The Rhodium complex after settling is of yellow brown colour. The elemental analysis shows that the mole ratio of the metal to ligand is 1 : 3. The method is useful even if 0.5 mg of rhodium is present.

All the reagents used were of analar grade.

The ligand was prepared as follows (Bagulev and Elvidge)².

Preparation: Phthalonitrile in ethanol was stirred for 9 hr with aqueous sodium hydrogen sulphide which has previously been saturated with H₂S. Addition of water precipitated a first crop of the product (37%) decomposition from 195°, whilst addition to the filtrate of 2N HCl almost to neutrality afforded less pure material (24%). Recrystallisation of the first crop from ethanol gave golden needles of 1-imino-3-thioisindoline (70% recovery).

Element analysis—Ligand :

	%C	%H	%N
Found	58.9	3.9	17.5
Required	59.3	3.7	17.3

The following stock solutions were prepared.

- (1) 1-imino-3-thioisindoline...about 0.1% sodium salt solution of the ligand in NaOH.
- (2) RhCl₃·3H₂O (Johnson-Matthey Co.)...A 0.25 W/V solution of hydrated RhCl₃·3H₂O in water (Standardized by thionide method).

Determination of Rhodium: A known volume 1 to 50 ml of solution No. 2 was taken and diluted (the amount of rhodium did not exceed too much). A freshly filtered solution No. 1 was added in excess. A yellow Brown precipitate of rhodium complex was digested on water bath for 10 min and filtered through a medium porosity sintered glass crucible. It was washed first with water several times and then with ethanol, dried at 70° to 105° or in a vacuum dessicator and weighed as Rh(C₈H₅N₂S)₃. The gravimetric factor for rhodium is 0.1754.

Elemental Analysis—Rhodium Complex.

	%C	%H	%N
Found	48.2	2.3	14.60
Required	49.0	2.5	14.28

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF RHODIUM WITH THE LIGAND

Sl. No.	mg Metal Taken	mg Metal Recovered	Error %
1.	5	5.00	—
2.	5	5.03	0.60
3.	5	5.05	1.00
4.	5	5.05	1.00
5.	10	9.95	0.50
6.	10	9.95	0.50
7.	10	10.10	1.00
8.	10	10.10	1.00
9.	20	20.25	1.25
10.	20	20.20	1.00
11.	20	20.10	0.5
12.	20	20.00	—

Interferences: There is generally no interference by the most common anions as SO₄²⁻, NO₃⁻, PO₄³⁻, Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻ and Cu⁺ only few cations interfere these includes Cu(II), Au(III), Pb, Ag, Hg(I), Hg(II), Bi, Cd, Pd(II), Pt(IV), Ni, Co, Tl, Ru, Ce, Zr.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data in table I indicate that the ligand can be effectively used as a promising gravimetric reagent for rhodium in macro and semi-micro quantities. It is easy to filter the precipitate. It is easy to bring the precipitate to constant weight within a period of half an hour.

The precision was fair, and the accuracy was generally within the permissible limits.

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Metal-Ligand Stability Constants of Chelate Compounds of 4-isonitroso-1-phenyl-3-methyl-pyrazolone-5 with Copper (II), Nickel (II), Cobalt (II) and Zinc (II)

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SPECTROPHOMETRIC studies on complex formation between iron(II) and 4-isonitroso-1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone-5 (4-IPMP) and the extraction and spectrophotometric studies of copper(II) with 4-IPMP have been reported by us earlier.^{1,2} We have now determined the stability constants of some metal chelates in aqueous-ethanol medium (50% by v/v) and 0.1M KNO₃ using Calvin-Bjerrum technique as applied by Irving and Rossotti³. The ligand and its metal chelates are insoluble in water.

Experimental and Results

The 4-IPMP was prepared as shown earlier¹. The standard solution of the reagent was prepared by dissolving the required amount of reagent in pure ethanol. Metal nitrate solutions were prepared by dissolving the corresponding nitrates of analytical grade. Potassium nitrate was used to keep the ionic strength constant. Standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide (E. Merck) solution was prepared according to the method of Allen and Low⁴. pH measurements were made with a Toshniwal pH meter.

The titrations were carried out in 50-50% (v/v) ethanol-water mixtures at 40° ± 1°. Three titrations viz., titration of (i) free nitric acid, (ii) free acid plus reagent, and (iii) free acid plus the reagent plus the metal ion, were carried out against 0.501M NaOH.

The practical proton-ligand stability constant, log ^PK^H, of the 4-IPMP has been obtained as the Bjerrum half-integral value from the formation curve. The same has also been calculated at different points using the equation:

$$\log {}^P K^H = B + \log \frac{\bar{n}_H}{1 - \bar{n}_H}$$

where *B* is the meter reading in aqueous ethanol. From the several log *K* values calculated for the system the average value was obtained as shown in Table 1. The half-integral value is found to be in good agreement with the average value.

From the metal-ligand formation curves (Fig. 1) it can be seen that the maximum values of \bar{n} for Co(II) and Zn(II) are less than 1, indicating that only 1:1

Fig. 1. Formation curves of bivalent metal complexes with 4-IPMP.

complexes are formed. For these systems log *K*₁ values have been obtained by Bjerrum half-integral method and by point-wise calculation using the equation:

$$\log K_1 = pL + \log \frac{\bar{n}}{1 - \bar{n}}$$

For the calculation of *pL* the following expression was used.

$$pL = \log \left[\frac{1 + {}^P K^H \frac{1}{\text{antilog } \bar{B}}}{T_L^\circ - \bar{n} \cdot T_M^\circ} \right]$$

where *T*_L[°] and *T*_M[°] are the initial total ligand and metal concentrations respectively.

The values of the formation constants obtained by these two methods are in good agreement (Table 1). In the Cu(II) and Ni(II) systems $\bar{n} > 1$, indicating that 1:1 and 1:2 complexes are formed. For these systems log *K*₁ and log *K*₂ values have been obtained by the least-squares method⁵. The results are given in Table 1.